

STUDIES IN CHALKONES : CHALKONES DERIVED FROM QUINACETOPHENONE MONO AND DIMETHYL ETHERS

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The work described in this paper relates to the chalkone formation from quinacetophenone monomethyl ether by its condensation with different aldehydes, the corresponding chalkones having been isolated for the first time along with the flavanones. Quinacetophenone dimethyl ether has been also condensed with various aldehydes and the chalkones have been obtained in good yields.

Kostanecki and his co-workers (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 773, 960, 2349; 1899, 32, 332, 1929; 1900, 33, 1480, 2509) condensed quinacetophenone monomethyl and monoethyl ethers with various methoxy- and ethoxy-aldehydes in presence of alkali and reported the exclusive formation of flavanones instead of the expected chalkones. A search of literature shows that hardly any work has been done on the chalkone formation from quinacetophenone monomethyl or monoethyl ether and it has been taken for granted that quinacetophenone monomethyl ether always condenses with aldehydes in presence of alkali giving directly the flavanones. This behaviour of monomethyl ether of quinacetophenone is in direct contrast to that of isomeric resacetophenone monomethyl ether (paenol) which condenses with aldehydes in presence of alkali giving easily the corresponding chalkones (Kostanecki and co-workers, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 698; 1900, 33, 332; 1904, 37, 1180, 4156; Jadhav and Vandrewala, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 28A, 127).

In connection with our work on chalkones derived from quinacetophenone (Vyas and Shah, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 273) we thought of investigating the chalkone formation from monomethyl ether of quinacetophenone, and undertook a study of its condensation with various aldehydes with a view to exploring the possibility of synthesising chalkones as they are hitherto unknown. The results obtained are presented in this communication.

We repeated the experiments according to the conditions used by Kostanecki and found that the flavanones were formed to a large extent. However, the crude flavanones obtained had to be crystallised several times before they could be obtained in pure state. The filtrates were highly coloured, indicating the presence of chalkones. It is evident that the chalkone formed undergoes immediate cyclisation under the conditions used. Kostanecki *et al.* have neither examined the coloured filtrates nor the mother-liquors after crystallisation of the flavanones.

We have now succeeded in obtaining the chalkones from the condensation of monomethyl ether of quinacetophenone with anisaldehyde, veratraldehyde and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde. To prevent the above cyclisation, we have carried out the above condensation in presence of cold alkali at room temperature (cf. Kostanecki, *loc. cit.*). The crude product obtained gave the characteristic reactions of a chalkone. The problem of its isolation presented certain difficulties. Several trial experiments were carried out. The crude mixture of chalkone and flavanone was extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide, in which only the chalkone was soluble. It was then precipitated by acidification, care being taken to prevent the rise of temperature. The yield of the chalkone, however, was poor in comparison with the amount of the flavanone

obtained. With a view to improving the yield of the chalcones, the condensation was investigated using different concentrations of alkali (20%, 40% and 80%) and it was observed that higher concentrations favoured the yield of the flavanones. The chalcones obtained are distinguished from the corresponding flavanones by the following reactions:—

- (i) They are easily soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide solution.
- (ii) They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with blood-red coloration.
- (iii) With alcoholic ferric chloride, they give reddish brown coloration indicating the presence of *ortho*-hydroxy group.
- (iv) They respond to Wilson's boric acid test and do not give colored reduction products with magnesium and hydrochloric acid (Seshadri and Rangaswami, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 16A, 129), and
- (v) They are isomerised to the corresponding known flavanones.

The constitution of the chalcone obtained from *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde was confirmed by preparing its benzoyl derivative which was found identical with the benzoyloxy-chalcone prepared from 2-benzoyloxy-5-methoxyacetophenone and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde by Russell's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 218). Further it was isomerised by hydrochloric acid to the corresponding flavanone identical with that of Kostanecki *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The reactions are shown diagrammatically below.

As the chalcones are obtained in small quantity along with the corresponding flavanones, it appears that the presence of 5-methoxy group makes 2-hydroxy group so reactive that the chalcone formed easily cyclises to the corresponding flavanone. The results obtained are very interesting as they supply the evidence that the chalcone is first formed and is then converted into the corresponding flavanone. The isolation of these chalcones brings the behaviour of quinacetophenone monomethyl ether in the same line with that of its isomers.

Chalcones derived from Quinacetophenone Dimethyl Ether.—A considerable amount of work has been reported in connection with the formation of chalcones derived from resacetophenone

dimethyl ether and various aldehydes (Gosche and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3502; Lal, *this Journal*, 1939, 16, 296; Jadhav and Vandrewala, *J. Bom. Univ.*, 1948, 16, part V, 45; Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1109). However, the chalkone formation from quinacetophenone dimethyl ether has remained practically uninvestigated. Quinacetophenone dimethyl ether has now been successfully condensed with anisaldehyde, veratraldehyde and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde using 75% potassium hydroxide as the condensing agent. As there is no free hydroxy group, the reaction is facile, the chalkones being obtained in good yield.

In the case of benzaldehyde, a yellow solid is obtained which gives the characteristic reactions of a chalkone but it could not be purified.

The chalkones derived from quinacetophenone have been already described (Vyas and Shah, *loc. cit.*), while those derived from quinacetophenone monomethyl and dimethyl ethers have been obtained for the first time. A noteworthy point that emerges from the study of some of the physical properties of these chalkones is that when the hydroxy groups of quinacetophenone are methylated, the colour of the chalkones gradually fades from red to orange to yellow e.g., chalkones derived from quinacetophenone are deep red; while those derived from quinacetophenone monomethyl ether are bright red; and those from quinacetophenone dimethyl ether are bright yellow. With regard to melting points, the methylation in the ketonic part of the molecule brings about the depression in the melting points of the hydroxy-chalkones. Quinacetophenone chalkones have higher melting points than those of the chalkones derived from quinacetophenone monomethyl ether; while those derived from quinacetophenone dimethyl ether melt at still lower temperatures than those derived from monomethyl ether. Roughly, the qualitative order of melting points is: hydroxy > monomethoxy > dimethoxy chalkones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Quinacetophenone mono and dimethyl ethers required for the purpose of investigation were prepared according to the method devised by Vyas and Shah (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 189).

2-Hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl-4'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—To a solution of quinacetophenone monomethyl ether (7 g.) and anisaldehyde (7 g.) in alcohol (70 c.c.) was added potassium hydroxide solution (45 c.c., 40%) with cooling under tap. The flask was covered and sealed with paraffin and left overnight at room temperature, the colour of the mixture changing from yellow to deep red. It was then diluted with ice water (700 c.c.) and acidified with ice-cold concentrated hydrochloric acid. The bright orange solid that separated was extracted four times with dilute sodium hydroxide (100 c.c., 5%). The residue was crystallised from ethyl acetate as colorless needles, m.p. 158°, identified as 6:4'-dimethoxyflavanone by the mixed m.p. with a sample prepared according to Kostanecki (*loc. cit.*).

The combined alkaline extracts were cooled to about 5° by adding sufficient ice and then acidified. On keeping in ice-bath for some time an orange flocculent solid separated; it was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 90-91°. It gave all characteristic reactions of a chalcone. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6 per cent).

6 : 4'-*Dimethoxyflavanone*.—The above chalcone (0.5 g.) was isomerised to the flavanone by using alcoholic hydrochloric acid (3%) as described in an earlier paper (Vyas and Shah, *loc. cit.*). The flavanone obtained was identical with the flavanone described above.

2-*Hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl-3':4'-methoxystyryl Ketone*.—Quinacetophenone monomethyl ether (7 g.) was condensed with veratraldehyde (7 g.) as before using the same proportion of alcohol and potassium hydroxide. The mixture of chalcone and flavanone was separated similarly. 6 : 3' : 4'-*Trimethoxyflavanone* was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. and the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 779) were found to be 176°.

The bright orange solid obtained by the acidification of the alkaline filtrate was crystallised from ethyl acetate as bright red shining needles, m.p. 136°. It is easily soluble in common organic solvents. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.7 per cent).

6 : 3' : 4'-*Trimethoxyflavanone*.—The above chalcone was cyclised to the flavanone by means of hydrochloric acid as described before. Pale yellow solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol as colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample were 176°.

2-*Hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl Ketone* was prepared from quinacetophenone monomethyl ether (7 g.) and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (7 g.) as before. The chalcone and flavanone were separated as usual. 6 : 2'-*Dimethoxyflavanone* was crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. and the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample prepared according to Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2346) were found to be 120°.

The chalcone crystallised from alcohol as red shining needles, m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6 per cent).

6 : 2'-*Dimethoxyflavanone* was prepared by the acid isomerisation of the above chalcone as before as pale yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample were 120°.

The benzoyl derivative of the chalcone, prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, separated as a pale yellow solid. After treatment with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, it crystallised from acetic acid as yellowish shining prisms, m.p. 124°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.8. $C_{24}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 74.2; H, 5.1 per cent).

2-*Benzoyloxy-5-methoxyacetophenone*.—Quinacetophenone monomethyl ether (5 g.) was benzoylated by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method. After usual treatment the solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 62°. It gives no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 70.9; H, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2 per cent).

2-*Benzoyloxy-5-methoxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl Ketone*.—2-Benzoyloxy-5-methoxyacetophenone (2.5 g.) was condensed with *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (2 g.) in dry ethyl acetate (40 c.c.)

by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas in an ice-bath for nearly 24 hours. During the reaction, the colorless solution changed to bright red and then to dark red. The solvent was then evaporated and the solid left was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and then crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow prismatic needles, m.p. and the mixed m.p. with the benzoyl derivative of 2-hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl ketone remaining unchanged.

Condensation of Quinacetophenone Dimethyl Ether with Benzaldehyde.—This condensation was tried under various conditions. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. 6-Methoxyflavanone isolated was crystallised from alcohol; m.p. and the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample prepared according to Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 773) were found to be 142°.

The chalkone obtained by acidifying the alkaline filtrate gave an orange solid which could not be crystallised. It turned to a thick oil. However, the crude chalkone gave all the characteristic reactions of a chalkone.

Chalkones derived from Quinacetophenone Dimethyl Ether

2:5-Dimethoxyphenyl-4'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—The solution of quinacetophenone dimethyl ether (5 g.) and anisaldehyde (4.1 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was gradually treated with potassium hydroxide solution (20 c.c., 75%) with cooling under tap, and left in a closed container for 24 hours. The resulting red solution was then diluted with ice water (500 c.c.). A thick oil separated which was well washed with water when it solidified; it was crystallised from benzene as bright yellow shining prisms, m.p. 97°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0 per cent).

2:5-Dimethoxyphenyl-3'-4'-dimethoxystyryl Ketone.—Quinacetophenone dimethyl ether (5 g.) was similarly condensed with veratraldehyde (5 g.) using alcohol (40 c.c.) and potassium hydroxide (20 c.c., 75%). The solid obtained was washed with very dilute alcohol and crystallised from benzene as bright yellow prisms, m.p. 92°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.0. $C_{19}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 69.5; H, 6.1 per cent).

2:5-Dimethoxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—A solution of quinacetophenone dimethyl ether (5 g.) and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (4.1 g.) in alcohol (40 c.c.) was treated with potassium hydroxide (20 c.c., 75%) and left overnight. Its colour changed from yellow to bright red. The chalkone isolated as before, crystallised from alcohol as bright yellow prisms, m. p. 74°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0 per cent).